

VOID BEHAVIOR IN COMPOSITE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

Aerospace applications of polymer matrix composites, with high specific strength and modulus, are being expanded from thin simple components to thick complex-shaped integrated structures. To fabricate these composite parts, autoclave processing is widely being used but is a complex process for thermosetting matrix resins such as epoxy or polyimide.

The objective of this study is to fabricate high quality composite laminates that are free of voids by optimizing of the autoclave cure cycle variables of temperature, pressure and time. In our work, the void formation and growth in uncured epoxy varnish were first visually observed under simulated cure cycles. It was found the initial moisture in epoxy resins easily creates voids, and the growth of voids was explained by using Boyle's Law and dissolution-diffusion theories. After measuring the diffusion and solubility coefficient of air and water to epoxy varnish, void sizes were calculated and the results agreed with the experimental data. On the basis of the theories, a computer simulation program was developed. This program can display the void size variations at any time during a simulated cure cycle and yields optimum autoclave cure cycles that can be used to fabricate void-free composite laminates.

Key words:Void;Epoxy;Composite;CureCycle;Dissolution-Diffusion

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of polymer matrix composites depends on the process of fabrication. To provide high quality thermosetting matrix laminates with no defects for aerospace applications, an optimization of autoclave cure cycle is important. The occurrence of voids in the final composite laminate is one of the critical problems. This is very critical in the fabrication of thick complex-shaped integrated structures. Many approaches to reduce voids have been experimentally studied. However very few have tried to establish an optimum cure cycle on a sound scientific basis.¹⁾²⁾

In this study, the void formation and growth in uncured epoxy-matrix resin were visually observed under the simulated cure cycles. On the basis of these experiments, a simple scientific basis has been formulated. The void behavior has been mathematically modeled and used to optimize commercial in-shop autoclave cure cycles providing void-free polymer matrix composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

To visualize the void behavior in the composite laminates, a uncured epoxy varnish was prepared for experimental observations. This epoxy system consists of a matrix resin from a high-

performance 180°C cure-type CFRP as shown in Table 1. The epoxy varnish was vacuum degassed for 30min. at 100°C before each test and observation.

2.2 Observation apparatus

To observe voids in the epoxy varnish, an apparatus shown in Fig. 1 was built. It consists of a vacuum chamber with pressure, and temperature controls and a microscope for real time monitoring of voids.

Table 1. Properties of matrix material

MATERIAL		EPOXY RESIN
RESIN VARNISH	VISCOSITY	10poise (at100°C)
	DENSITY	1.224 g/cm ³
	MOISTURE ABSORPTION	0.26% (at 20°C 50%RH) 20days
	SHRINKAGE	0.8%
CURED RESIN	T _g	199 °C
	FLEX. STRENGTH	25.1 kgf/mm ²
	MODULUS	450 kgf/mm ²

Figure 1. Apparatus for void observation

2.3 Procedure

During commercial autoclave processings, entrapped air, initial moisture and solvent are known to produce gaseous materials that can cause voids. In our experiments, we introduced entrapped air, absorbed moisture and MEK solvent by injection, absorption or mixing into the epoxy resin varnish. After containing gaseous materials, the varnish on the tray was introduced into the vacuum chamber and observed under simulated pressure-temperature cycles. The procedure for moisture absorption treatments is shown in Fig.2 and typical observed void behaviors are shown in Fig.3.

Figure 2. Procedure

Figure 3. Typical observed void behavior

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Void Formation

The epoxy varnish with 0.3-1.0% moisture absorption by weight was visually observed in the vacuum chamber under atmospheric pressure from RT to 120°C at a rate of temperature rise of 2°C / min. Every varnish, with 0.4% and up moisture absorption, showed void formations at temperature exceeding 100°C.

The varnish with 2.0% MEK solvent, which is a standard solvent content for prepregging, showed no visual void formation up to 120°C but showed voids only at vacuum conditions. Then we can conclude that the initial moisture in epoxy resins causes the void formation rather than the MEK solvent during the autoclave processing.

3.2 Void Volume Changes

3.2.1 Pressure Dependency

The volume changes of voids, that were formed by air injection into epoxy varnish, were visually observed under pressure changes at a constant temperature of 100°C which occurs in typical autoclave cure cycles. The volume of voids was calculated from the observed diameter of voids. The volume decrease under pressurized conditions is shown in Fig. 4 and the volume increase under vacuum conditions is shown in Fig.5 compared with Boyle's Law. The observed differences from Boyle's Law can be explained by the dissolution of the air into the epoxy varnish.

In order to reduce volume of voids at this stage of a cure cycle, enough pressurization to the epoxy matrix of composite laminates such as to prepreg lay-up stacks was found to be necessary.

Figure 4. Void under pressure increasing Figure 5. Void under Vacuum condition

3.2.2 Time Dependency

The volume changes of voids by air injection were also visually observed for 30minutes under a constant pressure and temperature. This also occurs in typical autoclave cure cycles. The results of void diameter changes under a constant pressure of 690kpa and at different temperatures of 80°C and 120°C are shown in Fig.6. The diameters of voids at both the temperatures decreased after 20 to 30min. hold. The void diameter at 120°C decreased faster than that of at 80°C.

These decreases were suspected to be due to gaseous air's diffusion into the epoxy varnish. In Fig.6, the curved lines of Fick's diffusion theory were also plotted and their tendencies agreed with the experimental results. The elimination of voids was observed after 20min. at 120°C hold. We attributed that the surface tension force collapsed the voids that had very small diameters.

Figure 6. Void under constant pressure

3.3 Discussion

3.3.1 Dissolution-Diffusion

On the basis of our experimental observations, we applied the dissolution-diffusion theories to explain the void behaviors. The void diameter can be expressed as follows.

$$d = d_0 - 2 \sqrt{\frac{D S P_g R T t}{\omega P}} \quad (1)$$

- d : Void diameter
- d_0 : Initial void diameter
- S : Solubility coefficient
- P_g : Partial pressure of a gas in the void
- R : Ideal gas constant
- D : Diffusion coefficient
- t : Time
- T : Temperature
- ω : Molecular weight of a gas
- P : Pressure of resin

To calculate the actual diameter of voids from Eq.(1), the diffusion and solubility coefficients of air and water to the epoxy varnish were obtained by what is called as the sorption method as shown in Fig.7. For the air, the diffusion and solubility coefficients of O_2 were measured and that of N_2 was calculated from the N_2/O_2 permeability ratio.³⁾ The measured coefficients of H_2O and O_2 are shown in Table 2. The calculated data of N_2 was negligibly small. Both coefficients of O_2 were much smaller than that of water. These indicate that air induced voids take more time to dissolve and diffuse in comparison with moisture induced voids. Therefore, in commercial processing, the lay-up of prepreg materials must be done so that air is not entrapped.

Figure 7. Schematic diagram of sorption apparatus

Table 2. Diffusion and Solubility coefficient

	D (cm^2/sec)	S ($cm^3/cm^3 \cdot Hg$)
H_2O	6.43×10^{-9}	2.06
O_2	2.68×10^{-9}	1.23×10^{-3}
N_2	$D \cdot S = 8.04 \times 10^{-13}$	

With these coefficients, void sizes were calculated for each condition. The results agreed with experimental data as shown in Fig.8. The diameter changes of moisture induced voids under 290kPa at 100°C were plotted. But in case of the air injected voids, some differences were found between our calculations and experimental observations as shown in Fig.9 because of moisture in the air.

Figure 8. Void diameter of experimental and calculated

Figure 9. Void diameter of experimental and calculated

3.3.2 Modeling Void Behavior

On the basis of the discussed dissolution-diffusion theories, the following Equation(2) is presented to provide a calculation of the void diameter at any pressure-temperature-time conditions.

$$d_{(t)} = (d_{(t-1)}^2 - 8 D S P_g t)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$d_{(t)}, d_{(t-1)}$: Void diameter	P_g : Partial pressure of a gas in the void
D : Diffusion coefficient	t : Time
S : Solubility coefficient	

By using the Equation(2), a modeling of the void behavior during autoclave cure cycles was achieved by computer calculations. In Fig.10, the resultant void diameter changes of a air injected void are shown during a simulated typical cure cycle and is compared with the experimental void observations. The result agreed with experiments and after calculations on several simulated cure cycles, the optimum cure cycle was found. This cure cycle would reduce air injected voids with diameters up to 1.0mm as shown in Fig.11. This modeling of void behavior can avoid expensive experiments and provides a simple and useful guideline to fabricate a void-free composite laminate for commercial in-shop autoclave processing.

Figure 10. Void diameter of calculated and experimental

Figure 11. Void behavior during the optimum cure cycle

4. CONCLUSIONS

The void formation and growth in uncured epoxy varnish for polymer matrix composites were visually observed under the simulated cure cycles. On the basis of these experiments, a simple scientific studies were performed including modeling of the void behavior. Our studies resulted in the following conclusions that can be used to optimize the commercial in-shop autoclave processings.

- (1) Initial moisture in uncured epoxy systems easily creates voids.
- (2) The void size behavior can be explained by using Boyle's Law and dissolution-diffusion theories. This depends on variables such as on pressure, temperature and time of cure cycle.
- (3) After modeling, a computer simulation program was developed to display the void size variations at any time during a simulated cure cycle. The calculated results agreed with the experimental data.
- (4) These indicate that the optimum cure cycles can be constructed to fabricate void-free composite laminates.

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